

THE TRAFFIC LIGHT SYSTEM TO SUPPORT FLEXIBILITY EXPLOITATION FROM STRESSED DISTRIBUTION GRID

Julien LE BAUT
AIT– Austria
Julien.Lebaut@ait.ac.at

Fabian LEIMGRUBER
AIT– Austria
Fabian.Leimgruber@ait.ac.at

Clemens KORNER
AIT– Austria
Clemens.Korner@ait.ac.at

Christoph GUTSCHI
cyberGRID – Austria
cg@cyber-grid.com

ABSTRACT

Virtual Power Plants can aggregate the flexibility of many individual resources to provide services to the Transmission System Operator for balancing services. However, without safeguards, the activation of bulk volume of flexibility can lead to violations of the operational limits in the distribution grid and affect the quality of supply. The Traffic Light System developed in the InteGrid project enables the Distribution System Operators to perform a technical validation of flexibility offers. In this paper, we introduce the Traffic Light Concept problematics and we present the architecture implementation. The concept is applied to a benchmarked medium-voltage network and the simulation results are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing variability and uncertainty related to the renewable generation is making it more difficult for the Transmission System Operators (TSO) to balance load and generation, leading to growing needs for ancillary services. The technological breakouts of the Distributed Energy Resources (DER) combined with the deployment of automation and monitoring technologies enable the provision of ancillary services by resources connected at the distribution network [1]. Virtual Power Plants (VPP), can aggregate the flexibility of single resources connected at the medium-voltage (MV) or low-voltage (LV) and offer it to actors such as Distribution System Operators (DSO), Transmission System Operators (TSO) or Balancing Responsible Parties (BRP). In the case that the flexibility is directly contracted by the DSO for voltage control or congestion management, the operation of distribution networks is safeguarded. However, in the case of the VPP providing services to a TSO, the DSO currently does not control the impact of the flexibility activation in the distribution network on daily basis. Rather, the DSO would deny pre-qualification of flexible units connected to under-dimensioned sections. As a result, available flexibility cannot be provided to ancillary service markets, reducing the market liquidity as well as the revenue potential of the flexible asset. At this stage, the volume of

flexibility proposed by the VPP are too limited to lead to violations of the operating rules – such as overvoltage or overloading – however, given the evolution of the regulatory framework in European Countries regarding the participation of aggregators in the regulated ancillary services market [2], it is crucial for the DSO to evaluate and validate the activation of flexibility services.

As proposed in the SmartNet project [3], the system prequalification, which consists in approving upfront the market participation, is a possible solution, but the fact that it is performed in ex-ante will lead to conservative assessments which can be a barrier for the exploitation of the flexibility.

The first step towards a secure use of the flexibility was performed in the ADDRESS project [4], where the technical validation of demand response products was performed in day-ahead and in real-time. This was later extended to other types of flexibilities and markets with the introduction of the Traffic Light concept [5], which defines a set of interactions and responsibilities between the market participants and the network operators for the use of flexibility located on the distribution network. The concept pointed out the necessity for aggregators to receive information about the current grid status. In the HybridVPP4DSO project [6], a Traffic Light System (TLS) was tested in a simulation environment to show the technical feasibility of the concept. In the INCREASE project [7], a simulation platform with a TLS was developed for demand response products. However, none of these projects have tested a Traffic Light System under real operating conditions.

In the scope of the H2020 project InteGrid [8], the Traffic Light concept has been refined to approach the current market designs and regulations in Portugal and Slovenia. The system has been developed and is being demonstrated in two pilot projects in both countries. The relevant European Guidelines such as the Electricity Balancing Guidelines [9] and the System Operations Guidelines [10] have been considered to match the expected regulatory evolutions. In this paper, we present the general framework and the implementation details of the TLS.

Simulations results are presented for one benchmarked network.

THE TRAFFIC LIGHT CONCEPT

The Traffic Light Concept refers to rules, roles and responsibilities defined between the TSO, the DSO and the VPP, for the regulated usage of flexibility products. The TLS refers to the technical system implemented to enable a safe activation of flexibility products. In the future, we will refer equally to both terms without distinction.

Objectives, concerns and constraints

The TLS has been designed with the following objectives:

- To ensure a non-discriminatory access to the market participants (the DSO acts as a Neutral Market Facilitator);
- To ensure a safe operation of the distribution network.
- To be scalable by handling multiple VPPs.

The concerns of each actor with respect to the TLS are given hereinafter:

- The DSO must prevent violations (such as overvoltage or over loadings) from occurring in its network. The rejection of a flexibility product should consider both the technical impact of the product and the price of this product.
- The TSO ensures the stability of the system hence the reliability of the market agents is the most relevant factor for him. The TSO cannot pay for the cost related to the rejection of flexibility offers.
- The VPP has a limited overview of his portfolio of flexible resources in day-ahead, due to the uncertainty of his forecasts. This uncertainty decreases when the number of pooled flexibilities increases, so the granularity of the flexible products (i.e. the pool size forming the flexible product) should be important enough for the VPP to benefit from a portfolio effect. The penalties applied in case of non-provision of the products should be limited in order to promote the participation of these actors in the manual frequency restoration reserve (mFRR) market. On the other side, this situation could lead to a lack of commitment from the VPP that could jeopardize the stability of the system.

Information Requirements for the different actors

TSO and market requirements

The TLS developed in InteGrid has been designed to perform the technical validation of flexibility offers for mFRR, although the pooling of flexibility for mFRR provision is not yet allowed in Portugal. We assume that the mFRR market is operated in day ahead. The TSO acts as the market operator and sends activation requests to the market agents (e.g. VPPs). The market products on the mFRR market have a time resolution of one hour – using longer product durations could penalize the flexibility pooling compared to conventional groups [2] – but no underperformance is allowed for the duration of the activation. The minimum bid size is equal to 1 MW and partial activation of the bids is allowed. The full activation time (FAT) is equal to 15 min and also relevant for deactivation. Unlike the DSO, the TSO usually doesn't need information regarding the exact location of the resources that provide balancing services, as long as they are located in the same control area (which is our case in the demo). The characteristics of the mFRR bids submitted to the mFRR market operator (TSO) contain the following information:

- The bid identifier
- The direction (upward or downward)
- The product interval (date and time)
- The capacity price (for reservation of flexibility)
- The energy price (for activation of flexibility)
- The quantity

In case of an activation of the bid, the TSO will communicate at least the following information to the market participant (i.e. the flexibility provider, VPP):

- The bid identifier
- The activation interval (date and time)
- The activation quantity

DSO requirements

The DSO must guarantee that a bid activated by the TSO does not lead to violations in the network, so it must obtain locational information about the resource(s) contributing to the activation by changing the active power feed-in of consumption. From the DSO's perspective, the smaller the granularity the better the accuracy at which it can evaluate the impact of flexibility on the network. However, this could lead to an increase of the computational burden and compromise the scalability of the system. Hence, the flexibility provider (e.g. the VPP) provides the flexibility information at the MV node level.

Given that the bids are submitted in day-ahead on the mFRR market, the DSO must forecast the network state for the time horizon covered by the market. In addition to the information sent to the TSO, the DSO receives the distribution network node identifier. Figure 1 below

provides a visual representation of the information structure.

Figure 1: Information model of the bid structure for the TSO (left) and the DSO (right)

VPP requirements

The VPP must submit the bids to the mFRR market in day-ahead, but it should have the possibility to modify the flexibility programs composing the bids in intraday, in order to gain some operational flexibility. The result (flags) of the technical validation received by the VPP must contain the maximum power that can be activated in the flexibility program.

Implementation of the TLS

Data exchange

The exchange of information between the TSO, the DSO and the VPP is realized via a cloud-based platform – the grid and market hub (gm-Hub) – developed in the scope of the InteGrid project. The VPP sends regularly to the gm-Hub the bids that need to be validated. The TLS requests the information to the gm-Hub and performs the technical validation of the bids. After the evaluation is performed, the results are sent-back to the VPP via the gm-Hub, as illustrated in Figure 2 below. The gm-hub allows to scale the concept to multiple VPPs, which may operate and pool different flexibilities in the network of the DSO in parallel.

Figure 2: Implementation of the TLS

Validation of flexibility programs

The technical validation of the flexibility programs is performed by an Optimal Power Flow algorithm (OPF) developed by INESC TEC in the scope of the InteGrid project. Additionally, the TLS receives load and generation forecasts for each MV node, through a forecasting algorithm developed by INESC TEC.

The functionality of the TLS is separated into two processes, namely the *ex-ante* evaluation and the *pre-activation* evaluation. In the *ex-ante* phase, which corresponds to the period occurring before the gate closure of the mFRR market, the TLS performs an evaluation of the flexibility programs every 15 minutes. In the *pre-activation* phase, the evaluation is triggered by the activation of a bid by the TSO. Note that the evaluation results have to be distinguished per direction; for instance, one grid section could be in the red-phase for one direction (e.g. upward in case of overvoltage) but it could be in the green-phase in the other direction (downward).

CASE-STUDY ON A BENCHMARKED NETWORK

Considered scenario

Network

The network which was used for the simulations is obtained from the CIGRE Benchmark [11]. For the simulations, the forecasts are obtained for a given period from 2018-08-26 to 2018-09-01 with a one-hour time resolution – the time horizon is 48 hours in the demo. All buses, except buses 1 and 3, have a varying load profile. PV is installed on buses 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, and 12. A wind turbine is installed on bus 8 and a combined heat and power (CHP) is connected to bus 8. It is assumed that the admissible voltage limits are +/- 5% for the MV.

Flexibility products

We assume that a VPP is offering flexibility services in the distribution network for the mFRR market. The volume of flexibility offered is intentionally high in order to demonstrate the potential of the TLS; the quantity might not always be realistic. In a first case, it is assumed for this example that the quantity of power is the same for each hour. The network is operated radially, and we assume that the topology is unchanged.

Table 1 below presents the bids that have been proposed. Positive quantities correspond to an upward direction of the flexibilities whereas negative values related to the downward direction. Note that the time duration in the following analysis is 4 hours to capture inter-hour dynamics. The product duration is still 1 hour, which means that Bid_a should be thought of as a group of 4 bids.

Table 1: Flexibility bids schedules

Bid id	Flexibility id	Price (€/MWh)	Quantity (MW)	Bus id	Duration (hh:mm)
Bid_a	Flex_a13	50	0.5	13	08:00 –
	Flex_a14		2.5	14	12:00
Bid_b	Flex_b13	60	2.5	13	08:00 –
	Flex_b14		0.5	14	12:00
Bid_c	Flex_c13	50	-4.0	13	14:00 –
	Flex_c14		-0.5	14	18:00
Bid_d	Flex_d13	60	-0.5	13	14:00 –
	Flex_d14		-4.0	14	18:00

Simulations results

Ex-ante evaluation

In these simulations, the bids are received in day-ahead. The receiving of the bids triggers the ex-ante evaluation of the TLS. In Figure 3 the ex-ante results are shown for the voltage of bus 14 for an upward evaluation. The voltage profile of the bus without activated flexibilities is marked with a triangular marker and shows a typical PV profile. If all proposed upward flexibilities would be activated, the voltage limit of 1.05 p.u. would be violated from 08:00 to 12:00. In the wake of the ex-ante evaluation, the OPF of the TLS suggests a curtailment of the flexibilities to such extent that no violations will occur.

Figure 3: Voltage profile of bus 14 for an upward evaluation

Figure 4 shows the curtailment of the flexibilities for the upward evaluation, where suggested curtailments are visualized with a stiped pattern and allowed activations are drawn with solid colour. Remarkably, the TLS optimizes the curtailment in an economical favourable way. For this reason, Bid_a is less curtailed than Bid_b because it is cheaper.

Figure 4: Curtailment of the upward flexibilities

The line loading of the section line that connects buses 12 and 13 is plotted in Figure 5 for the ex-ante evaluation of the downward bids. Without curtailment of the proposed flexibilities, the activation of all flexibilities would cause a violation of the maximum line loading constraint between 16:00 and 18:00. As before, the OPF calculates a curtailment schedule, where all constraint violations get removed.

Figure 5: Line loading of the line connecting buses 12 and 13 for a downward evaluation

The curtailment of the flexibilities for the downward evaluation is depicted in Figure 6. This plot shows a partial curtailment of Flex_d14 from 16:00 to 18:00. This makes economical sense because Flex_d14 is part of the pricier bid. The TLS responds to an ex-ante request with two-fold information: the size of the required curtailment and traffic lights for the buses with flexibilities. In this example, bus 13 has a green traffic light for all four hours because no flexibility is curtailed on this bus. Bus 14 has a green traffic light from 14:00 to 16:00 but becomes marked with an orange traffic light for the following two hours due to the partial curtailment.

Figure 6: Curtailment of the downward flexibilities

Pre-activation evaluation

After gate closure, the TLS receives the final bids which are valid for the coming day and the pre-activation evaluations. An exemplary downward pre-activation is shown in Figure 7. In this example, the TSO requests an activation of Bid_c between 17:00 and 18:00 which activates Flex_c13 with -4 MW and Flex_c14 with -0.5 MW. The activation triggers a pre-activation evaluation of the TLS for this hour. The activated flexibilities Flex_c13 and Flex_c14 are marked with a black striped overlay going from top-right to bottom-left. The TLS responds to the pre-activation request with the quantity of the remaining flexibilities that can be activated without causing constraint violations. This available quantity of the non-activated flexibilities is shown with black circular overlays. In this example, additionally to the flexibilities of Bid_c, Flex_d13 could be activated with -0.5 MW and Flex_d14 with -2.66 MW without causing grid violations. The TLS curtails Flex_d14 with -1.34 MW which is visualized with red stripes going from top-left to bottom-right. In this example, the quantities of the non-activated flexibility are the same as the quantities obtained from the ex-ante evaluation from the previous day. In general, these values could differ due to forecast deviations.

Figure 7: Downward pre-activation evaluation for the activation of Bid_c

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The first in-house tests of the showed very promising results and they demonstrated the potential of the TLS. The notable difference with the previous Traffic Light Concept is that the market participation is not blocked in

day-ahead – the TLS blocks only the activation of the flexibility program – so intraday corrections can be made by the VPP. The TLS will be demonstrated in Portugal and in Slovenia in 2019, furthermore cost-benefits and Scalability and Replicability analysis will be performed to generalize the results. Further developments of the TLS include the extension of the system to other services (e.g. aFRR) since the current traded volume of mFRR are too limited to demonstrate the economic interest of the system.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to this work is being carried out as a part of the InteGrid project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No. 731218.

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